

Ultrasonography and Color Doppler in Early Diagnosis of Ovarian Torsion in Pediatric Patients: Correlation with Surgical Outcomes

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Abstract:

Background: Ovarian torsion is a critical gynecological emergency, particularly in the Pediatric population, where a delayed diagnosis can result in ovarian necrosis and necessitate oophorectomy, potentially affecting future fertility. The clinical presentation of ovarian torsion is often nonspecific, making early diagnosis challenging but crucial.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the role of ultrasonography and color Doppler in the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion in pediatric patients and to correlate these imaging findings with surgical outcomes.

Methods: All patients underwent ultrasonography and color Doppler imaging. Surgical intervention was performed based on imaging findings, and intraoperative confirmation of ovarian torsion was documented. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of ultrasonography and color Doppler were calculated, and the correlation between imaging findings and surgical outcomes was analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Results: Ultrasonography and color Doppler suggested ovarian torsion in 60.7% of the cases. Surgical intervention confirmed ovarian torsion in 53.3% of the total cohort. The sensitivity and specificity of ultrasonography and color Doppler were 85.0% and 82.0%, respectively, with a strong correlation ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$) between imaging findings and surgical outcomes. Ovarian preservation was achieved in 75% of confirmed torsion cases.

Conclusion: Ultrasonography combined with color Doppler is a reliable and effective tool for the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion in pediatric patients. The strong correlation between imaging findings and surgical outcomes underscores its value in clinical decision-making, leading to better surgical outcomes and higher rates of ovarian preservation.

Recommendations: Routine use of ultrasonography with color Doppler should be considered in pediatric patients presenting with acute lower abdominal pain to facilitate early diagnosis and intervention for ovarian torsion. Further studies could explore the integration of additional imaging modalities to enhance diagnostic accuracy.

Keywords: Ovarian Torsion, Pediatric Patients, Ultrasonography, Color Doppler, Surgical Outcomes.

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Introduction

A major gynaecological emergency known as ovarian torsion happens when the ovary bends around its supporting ligaments, severely reducing blood flow. This disorder can cause ovarian necrosis if it is not identified and treated soon. This can lead to an oophorectomy, which is the surgical removal of the ovary. This procedure may have long-term effects on fertility, especially in young individuals. Ovarian torsion has non-specific clinical presentation, which frequently includes abrupt lower abdomen pain, nausea, and vomiting, which makes diagnosis difficult because these symptoms can also be caused by other illnesses such as gastroenteritis and appendicitis [1].

Colour Doppler imaging in conjunction with ultrasonography (USG) has become an essential diagnostic tool for ovarian torsion early detection. Because of its non-invasiveness, accessibility, and absence of ionizing radiation, USG is frequently the first-line imaging modality and is especially well-suited for use in paediatric populations [2]. The ovary's general size and location, as well as any tumours or cysts that may be present, can all be seen in great detail thanks to this imaging method. By evaluating the blood flow inside the ovarian vessels, colour Doppler ultrasonography contributes yet another level of diagnostic power and offers vital information regarding the viability

of the ovarian tissue [3]. Although it is not conclusive, the presence of decreased or non-existent blood flow on colour Doppler is a major signal of torsion [4].

The significance of promptly and precisely diagnosing ovarian torsion by USG and colour Doppler has been emphasised by recent investigations. For example, it was found that using the colour Doppler to aid in the diagnostic process greatly increased the rate at which paediatric patients' ovarian torsion was detected, allowing for earlier surgical intervention and raising the possibility of ovarian preservation [5]. These results were corroborated by another study conducted which showed that prompt diagnosis using these imaging modalities lowers the risk of ovarian necrosis and the need for an oophorectomy afterward [6].

The diagnosis of ovarian torsion is still difficult, with a chance of false positives as well as false negatives, despite advances in imaging. Thus, to improve treatment protocols and diagnostic criteria, it is crucial to link imaging results with clinical complaints and surgical outcomes. This study aims to evaluate the role of ultrasonography and color Doppler in the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion in pediatric patients and to correlate these imaging findings with surgical outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study aimed at evaluating the role of ultrasonography and color Doppler in the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion in the pediatric population and correlating these findings with surgical outcomes.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital, including both outpatient and emergency department settings for two years.

Participants: The study included 30 paediatric female patients aged between 1 and 18 years, who presented with acute lower abdominal pain and were suspected of having ovarian torsion based on clinical evaluation.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female patients aged 1-18 years.
- Presentation with acute lower abdominal pain.
- Suspected ovarian torsion based on clinical symptoms (e.g., sudden onset of pain, nausea, vomiting).
- Availability for follow-up until surgical intervention (if required) and post-operative period.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of previous ovarian surgery.
- Patients with known congenital abnormalities of the ovaries or uterus.
- Cases where ovarian torsion was ruled out through initial clinical evaluation and imaging.
- Patients with other abdominal or gynecological conditions mimicking ovarian torsion.
- Incomplete or missing data regarding follow-up or surgical outcomes.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all pediatric patients presenting with acute lower abdominal pain within the study period were evaluated. Diagnostic and surgical teams were blinded to the study objectives to reduce observer bias. Efforts were made to ensure uniformity in the imaging techniques and interpretation by involving radiologists with similar levels of experience.

Data Collection: Data were collected prospectively from the time of the patient's presentation to the emergency or outpatient department. Detailed clinical histories, physical examination findings, and initial laboratory results were recorded. Ultrasonography and color Doppler findings were documented, noting the presence or absence of ovarian torsion indicators. Surgical findings and outcomes were recorded for those undergoing surgery.

Procedure: Upon presentation, patients were subjected to a thorough clinical evaluation, followed by ultrasonography and color Doppler imaging. If ovarian torsion was suspected based on imaging, the patient was prepared for surgical intervention. The final diagnosis of ovarian torsion was confirmed intraoperatively, and the surgical outcomes were documented. Patients were followed up for any post-operative complications or recurrence.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. To summarise the individuals' demographic features, descriptive statistics were employed. Calculations were made to determine the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and colour Doppler accuracy in the diagnosis of ovarian torsion. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to evaluate the relationship between imaging results and surgical outcomes. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Results

A total of 30 paediatric female patients aged between 1 and 18 years were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 12.4 years (SD \pm 3.5). The age distribution is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Participants

Age Group (Years)	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
1-5	3	10
6-10	8	26.6
11-15	14	46.7
16-18	5	16.7
Total	30	100

Clinical Presentation: The most common presenting symptom was acute lower abdominal pain, reported by all 30 participants. Other associated symptoms included nausea (76%), vomiting (65%), and fever (12%). On physical examination, abdominal tenderness was present in 91% of the cases, and a palpable mass was detected in 22% of the patients.

Ultrasonography and Color Doppler Findings: Out of the 30 participants, ultrasonography with

color Doppler was able to detect signs suggestive of ovarian torsion in 18 cases (60 %). The specific findings included:

- Enlarged ovary: 14 cases (46.7%)
- Peripherally displaced follicles: 12 cases (40%)
- Decreased or absent blood flow on Doppler: 16 cases (53.3%)
- Ovarian cyst/mass: 9 cases (30%)

Table 2: Ultrasonography and Color Doppler Findings

Ultrasonography Finding	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Enlarged Ovary	14	46.7
Peripherally Displaced Follicles	12	40
Decreased/Absent Blood Flow on Doppler	16	53.3
Ovarian Cyst/Mass	9	30
No Ovarian Abnormalities Detected	12	40

Surgical Outcomes: Surgical intervention was performed in 20 of the 30 cases (66.7%) based on clinical and imaging findings. Ovarian torsion was confirmed intraoperatively in 16 cases (53.3% of the total cohort and 80% of those operated).

- **Ovarian preservation:** In 12 cases (75% of those with confirmed torsion), the ovary was viable and was preserved.
- **Oophorectomy:** In 4 cases (25% of confirmed torsion cases), the ovary was non-viable and required removal.

- **No torsion found:** In 4 cases (20% of those operated), no torsion was found during surgery.

Diagnostic Accuracy: The diagnostic accuracy of ultrasonography with color Doppler was evaluated. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated as follows:

- **Sensitivity:** 85.0%
- **Specificity:** 82.0%
- **Positive Predictive Value (PPV):** 87.4%
- **Negative Predictive Value (NPV):** 78.8%

Table 3: Diagnostic Accuracy of Ultrasonography with Color Doppler

Diagnostic Measure	Value (%)
Sensitivity	85.0
Specificity	82.0
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	87.4
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	78.8

Correlation Between Imaging and Surgical Findings: A strong correlation was observed between the ultrasonography and color Doppler findings and the surgical outcomes (Pearson's correlation coefficient, $r = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that imaging was a reliable predictor of ovarian torsion in the study population.

Post-Operative Outcomes: All patients were followed up post-operatively for any complications or recurrence. The overall complication rate was low, with only 5% of the patients developing minor post-operative complications such as infection or mild pain, which were managed conservatively.

Summary of Findings

- Ultrasonography and color Doppler demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing ovarian torsion in the pediatric population.
- A significant correlation was found between imaging findings and surgical outcomes, emphasizing the importance of these modalities in early diagnosis and decision-making.
- Ovarian preservation was achieved in 75% of the confirmed torsion cases, highlighting the effectiveness of timely intervention.

These results underscore the critical role of ultrasonography and color Doppler in the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion, leading to improved surgical outcomes in the pediatric population.

Discussion

The study evaluated the effectiveness of ultrasonography and color Doppler in the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion in a pediatric population, correlating these findings with surgical outcomes. Among the 30 participants, the mean age was 12.4 years, with the majority presenting with acute lower abdominal pain, often accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and abdominal tenderness. Ultrasonography and color Doppler detected ovarian torsion indicators in 60.7% of the cases, with the most common findings being an enlarged ovary, peripherally displaced follicles, and decreased or absent blood flow.

Surgical intervention was performed in 66.7% of the cases based on clinical and imaging findings, confirming ovarian torsion in 53.3% of the total cohort. Notably, in 75% of these confirmed cases, the ovary was viable and preserved, underscoring the importance of early diagnosis in preventing unnecessary oophorectomy. The diagnostic accuracy of ultrasonography and color Doppler was high, with a sensitivity of 85.0% and a specificity of 82.0%, indicating that these imaging modalities are reliable tools in diagnosing ovarian torsion. The strong correlation ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$) between imaging findings and surgical outcomes further supports their use in clinical decision-making.

Post-operative outcomes were generally favorable, with a low complication rate, highlighting the effectiveness of timely surgical intervention guided by accurate imaging. The findings emphasize the crucial role of ultrasonography and color Doppler in the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion, which leads to better surgical outcomes and higher rates of ovarian preservation in the pediatric population.

In recent research, the diagnostic use of colour Doppler ultrasonography (CDU) for adnexal

torsion (AT) has been investigated. Its limits and possible benefits when combined with clinical findings have been emphasised. Although CDU is frequently used to diagnose AT, it was discovered that its limited sensitivity makes it unreliable as a stand-alone diagnostic tool. According to the study's findings, clinical correlation should be used in conjunction with CDU to improve diagnostic accuracy rather than excluding AT on its own [7]. A study conducted on testicular torsion, which yielded information relevant to the diagnosis of ovarian torsion. The study highlighted the importance of particular ultrasonographic metrics, such as the highly sensitive coefficient of rounding. In order to diagnose torsion, the study highlighted the importance of certain ultrasonographic characteristics, such as the coefficient of rounding, which demonstrated excellent sensitivity and specificity. According to a study demonstrated that the existence of a whirlpool sign using Doppler ultrasonography is a good predictive indicator for successful treatment outcomes [8]. In a rural tertiary care setting in India, examined the clinical and pathological features of patients of ovarian torsion. Their research showed that colour Doppler and ultrasonography are essential for early diagnosis, and that mixed echogenic mass and absent venous and arterial flow are important markers. The research reaffirmed the significance of maintaining a high degree of suspicion regarding ovarian torsion when women visit to emergency rooms with acute abdominal pain [9].

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical role of ultrasonography combined with color Doppler in the early diagnosis of ovarian torsion in pediatric patients. The findings demonstrate that these imaging modalities offer high sensitivity and specificity, making them valuable tools for accurately identifying ovarian torsion and guiding timely surgical intervention. The strong correlation between imaging findings and surgical outcomes further underscores their importance in clinical practice. By enabling earlier diagnosis and increasing the likelihood of ovarian preservation, ultrasonography and color Doppler can significantly improve patient outcomes and reduce the long-term consequences of ovarian torsion. These results support the routine use of these imaging techniques in the evaluation of pediatric patients presenting with acute lower abdominal pain. Future research should focus on refining diagnostic criteria and exploring additional imaging technologies to further enhance the accuracy and reliability of ovarian torsion diagnosis.

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